

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEAVES
OF TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA BY USING SOXHLATION AND
MACERATION PROCESS AND THEIR ANTIOXIDANT
ACTIVITY DETERMINATION**Venkata Krishna Raju¹, Lakshmi Supriya Darapureddi², Aravind Eswar Iruvanti³, Bhavya Sri Soma⁴, Naga Poojitha Devarakonda⁵Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis, Bapatla college of pharmacy,
Bapatla - 522101**Abstract:**

Tinospora cordifolia is referred as Giloe and Guduchii, with significant importance in the traditional medicinal systems. It is dioeciously plant, which is mostly used in Ayurvedic system and also known as a 'Rasayans' of medicinal system. It develops immune system of the body and protect against infection. The aim of this study is carried out to analyse the phytochemical compounds in leaves and stem extracts of *T. cordifolia* by using phytochemical screening tests and estimate TFC by using aluminium chloride method in the sample extracts. The leaf extracts (maceration & soxhlation) of *T. cordifolia* expressed the presence of several phytochemicals viz., flavonoids, amino acids, diterpenes, protein, saponins and carbohydrates. The result of phytochemical screening tests revealed that diterpenes and carbohydrates are positive in all extracts of *T. cordifolia*, but flavonoids and saponins only present in methanol and ethanol extracts. TFC of *T. cordifolia* was higher in ethanolic leaves extracts than methanolic leaves extracts. The studies justify that *T. cordifolia* use in traditional medicines. The investigation further proposed that the phytochemicals present in leaves of *T. cordifolia*, which can be use as natural antioxidants in medicinal drugs. The antioxidant activity was also determined by using H₂O₂ scavenging.

Key Words: TFC - Total Flavonoid Content, NaOH – Sodium Hydroxide, AlCl₃- Aluminium Chloride, *Tinospora Cordifolia*, V/v – volume per volume

Corresponding author:

Raju Venkata Krishna ,
Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis
Bapatla college of pharmacy, Bapatla
rajuvenkatakrishna@gmail.com
Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla - 522101

QR code

Please cite this article in press Raju Venkata Krishna et al., *Qualitative And Quantitative Analysis Of Leaves Of Tinospora Cordifolia By Using Soxhlation And Maceration Process And Their Antioxidant Activity Determination.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).

INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal chemistry is the design and discovery of new compounds is a primary objective which is suitable for use as drugs. This process involves a team of workers from a wide range of disciplines chemistry, biology, biochemistry, pharmacology, mathematics, medicine and computing. The design of a new drug not only requires design process but also the synthesis of a new drug, a method of administration. Docking is the process by which the two molecules fit together in 3D space. This is useful for the drug design and binding of protein with drug particular functional group. Phytochemistry was developed constant in zwenger in the years between 1814-1885. This study is used for the identification of chemical nature of the reactions and interaction involved in drug therapy. The researchers have focused on natural anti-oxidants and numerous crude extracts and pure natural compounds have been recognized to have beneficial effects against free radicals in biological systems as anti-oxidants. The medicinal value of these plants lies in some chemical active substances that produce a definite physiological action on the human body. The most important of these chemically active (bioactive) constituents of plants are: alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids and phenolic compounds. Plant oils and extracts have been used for a wide variety of purposes for many thousands of years¹. Guduchi, commonly known as Giloe, in mythology. This botanical is a large deciduous perennial climber with large succulent stems and papery bark, sending down long, pendulous fleshy roots as it climbs. It is valued for its huge therapeutical term refers to the heavily elixir. Since each part of Guduchi has some medicinal property, it is very much commercially exploitable. Present review explores medico historical aspects of Guduchi with its therapeutic potentials and the modern scientific information supporting the same².

Tinospora cordifolia (Wild.) Miers, commonly known as Guduchii s highly potent herbs used since ancient times by physicians to combat diabetes. Giloy or Heart-leaved Moonseed is a genetically different, large, transitory clamber shrubs belong to menispermaceae family. It is distributed throughout the tropical Subcontinent and China, ascending to an altitude of 300 m. In Ayurvedic medicinal system, Guduchi is also known as MEDHYA RASAYANA (learning & memory enhancer) and the roots of *T. cordifolia* is used traditionally for its anti-stress activity³. It is used as most divine shrubs for its enormous properties like Anti-inflammatory, Antiarthritic, Anti Osteoporotic, Anti-Allergic, Antioxidant, Antineoplastic, Radioprotective, Antipyretic, Antiinfective, Antihyperglycemic, Immunomodulatory,

Hepatoprotective, Diuretic, Antileprotic, Gastrointestinal, Antiulcer, Antifertility, Osteoprotective and Cardioprotective activities⁴. Drugs from the plants are easily available, less expensive, safe and efficient and rarely have side effects⁵. Medicinal plants contain some organic compounds which provide definite physiological action on the body and these bioactive substances include tannins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, terpenoids, steroids and flavonoids. These compounds are synthesized by primary or rather secondary metabolism of living organisms. Secondary metabolites are widely used in the human therapy, veterinary, agriculture, scientific research and countless other areas⁷⁻⁸.

EXTRACTION:

Extraction involves the separation of medicinally active portions of plant or animal tissues from the inactive or inert compounds by using selective solvents in standard extraction procedures.

Extract: Extracts can be defined as preparations of crude drugs which contain all constituents which are soluble in the solvent⁹.

Steps Involved in the Extraction of Medicinal Plants:

In order to extract medicinal ingredients from plant material, the following sequential steps are involved:

1. Size reduction
2. Extraction
3. Filtration
4. Concentration
5. Drying¹⁰.

VARIOUS TYPES OF METHODS OF EXTRACTION:

1. Infusion
2. Decoction
3. Digestion
4. Maceration
5. Continuous hot extraction
6. Percolation
7. Supercritical fluid extraction
8. Counter current extraction
9. Microwave assisted extraction¹¹.

MACERATION:

In this process, the whole or coarsely powdered crude drug is placed in a stoppered container with the solvent and allowed to stand at room temperature for a period of at least 3 days with frequent agitation until the soluble matter has dissolved. The mixture then is strained, the marc (the damp solid material) is pressed, and the combined liquids are combined liquids are clarified by filtration or decantation after standing¹².

Process of maceration:

- Plant material (crushed or cut small or moderately coarse powder)
- Placed in a closed Vessels
- Whole of the selected solvent (menstruum) added
- Allowed to stand for seven days shaking occasionally
- Liquid strained off
- Solid residue (marc) pressed (recover as much as occlude solution)
- Clarified by subsidence or filtration
- Evaporation and concentration

Merits:

- Skilled operator not required
- For substances that require only extended contact time solvent and that are minimally soluble in solvent
- For low priced drugs and less potent drugs.

Demerits:

- Time-consuming and incomplete extraction¹³.

CONTINUOUS HOT EXTRACTION (Soxhlet extraction):

Soxhlet extraction is a modern extraction technique in which we circulate the same solvent through the extractor several times. It is a continuous extraction technique but we call it a series of short maceration. Soxhlet extractor needs the desired compound to be soluble in the solvent at a high temperature. It makes the extraction process much more efficient than that of the traditional method. It extracts the components using the condensed vapours of the solvent. The condensed vapours come in contact with the sample powder and the soluble part in the powder gets mixed with the solvent. The solvent containing the dissolved component, is siphoned into the boiler below residual solvent then drains out of the porous cup, as fresh solvent drops continue to fall into porous cup and the cycle repeats. However, it is not an appropriate technique for thermolabile plant compounds since consistent shaking is not possible¹².

Merits:

- Large amount of drug can be extracted with much smaller quantity of solvent.
- Tremendous economy in terms of time, energy & ultimately financial inputs.
- Small scale used a batch –process.
- Becomes more economical when converted into continuous extraction.
- Procedure on large scale.

Demerits:

- Physical nature of drug.
- Solvent.
- Chemical constituent of drug¹³.

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Antioxidant means against oxidation. Any substance at low concentrations compared to that of an oxidizable substrate that significantly delays or prevents oxidation of that substrate is called as antioxidant. Antioxidants play a vital role in preserving the quality of food and maintaining health of human being²¹.

Classification of antioxidant:

Broadly, there are five major types of antioxidants are described below:

- Primary antioxidants or chain breaking antioxidants are those compounds, mainly phenolic substances that terminate the free radical chains in lipids oxidation and function as hydrogen and electron donors.
- Oxygen scavengers are those substances which react with oxygen and can thus remove it in a closed system. e.g., ascorbic acid (vitamin C).
- Secondary antioxidants are those compounds which function by decomposing the lipid hydroperoxides into stable end products.
- Enzymatic antioxidants are those enzymes which function either by removing dissolved or head space oxygen, e.g., super oxide dismutase.
- Chelating agents are synergistic substances which greatly enhance the action of phenolic antioxidants. e.g., citric acid, amino acid and phospholipids such as cephalin²².

DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

- 1) In-vitro Estimation of Antioxidant Activity.
- 2) In-Vivo Estimation of Antioxidant Activity²³.

DRUG PROFILE:

Tinospora cordifolia also known as "Guduchi" in Sanskrit, is a versatile, large, evergreen, tree that grows in the highlands and belongs to the Menispermaceae family. The male flowers are collected in raceme or racemose panicles, while the female flowers are isolated². Its reported medicinal properties such as anti-diabetic, antiperiodic, antispasmodic, anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, anti-oxidant,

anti-stress, anti-leprotic, antimalarial, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory and antineoplastic activity³. *Tinospora cordifolia* contains tinosporaside, jatrorrhizine, palmatine, berberine, tembetarine, tinocordifolioside, phenylpropene disaccharides, choline, tinosporaacid, tinospora, tinosporin and tinosporide⁴.

Guduchii, commonly known as Giloe. It is valued for its huge therapeutic potential thousands of years back in ayurvedic literature, Its therapeutic strength lies in its rejuvenating and strengthening properties while detoxifying and cleansing the whole system, specifically via liver. Since each part of *guduchii* has some medicinal property. It is very much commercially exploitable⁵.

NUTRITIONAL VALUES:

Along with rich protein and dietary fibre contents appreciable levels of major and minor elements namely Zn, Mn, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Br and Sr are found in this herb, that acts as micronutrients for health recovery purpose, *Guduchi* stem provides sufficient carbohydrate (61.66%), low fat (3.1%) and 292.54 calories per 100g. Proximate and elemental analysis of its stem revealed rich nutritive composition essential for immunomodulation, body building and health restoration. A popular dosage form of *Guduchi* - *Guduchi Satva* is also reported to possess rich nutrients viz. fat, protein, dietary fibres, energy contents, Ca, Fe, as 0.14g, 0.16g, 288.8cal, 70 mg⁶.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection:

Tinospora cordifolia (leaves) were collected from the medicinal garden. The plant was authenticated as *Tinospora cordifolia* by DR.D. RAJAKUMARI, Professor and Head, Department of Botany, Bapatla college of arts and sciences, The glass wares were washed properly rinsed with their respective solvents and dried then the collected leaves are dried properly⁹.

Plant extraction:

The plant were taken and washed with normal water gently to separate soil particles and other contaminant and again washed with distilled water, Leaves were collected and dried at 37°C¹⁰. Plants have active phytochemical constituents, which loses their activity due to exposure to sunlight. Therefore, we avoided the sunlight exposure during the process. The dried plant sample was cut off into small pieces and grounded to powdered form This powdered sample of plant was used for extraction process¹¹.

Preparation of sample extract:

Powdered and dried plant sample was extracted separately with different solvents by using Maceration and Soxhlation extraction processes.

Maceration process:

Crude plant extract was prepared by maceration process. About 10gm of powdered plant material was weighed and taken in a stoppered container with the different solvents (ethanol, methanol & chloroform) and then allowed to stand at room temperature for a period of 3 days with frequent agitation until the soluble matter was dissolved. The mixture was strained and the combined liquids are clarified by filtration. After that the extract was taken in a beaker and kept on hot plate and heated at 30-40°C till all the solvent got evaporated¹².

Soxhlation extraction or Hot Continuous extraction:

Crude plant extract was prepared by Soxhlet extraction method. About 10 gm of powdered plant material was uniformly packed into a thimble and extracted with 250ml of different solvents separately. Solvents used were methanol, ethanol and chloroform. The process of extraction continues for 24 hours or till the solvent in siphon tube of an extractor becomes colourless. After that the extract was taken in a beaker and kept on hot plate and heated at 30-40°C till all the solvent got evaporated. Dried extract was kept in refrigerator at 4°C for further use in phytochemical analysis¹³.

Phytochemical qualitative analysis:

Plant extracts, which were freshly prepared were subjected to standard phytochemical analysis to detect the phytochemical constituent's viz. flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, proteins, carbohydrates and sugars¹⁴.

Preparation of the test sample:

The test solution was prepared by taking 1 gm of the extract in 25ml of ethanol.

Test for carbohydrates:

There are some tests performed for carbohydrates.

a) Molisch's test: A solution of carbohydrate in water was treated with alcoholic solution of alpha naphthol. On addition of concentrated sulphuric acid along the side of test tube a purple ring is formed on the junction before aqueous layer. With insoluble carbohydrates the colour will produce on shaking the reaction mixture.

b) Benedict's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken in a test tube. On addition of small quantity of benedict's solution & mixed properly. Then the sample mixture was boiled for two minutes and cool it. If carbohydrates present in the sample it forms red precipitate.

c) Barfoed's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken in a test tube. On addition of small quantity of Barfoed's solution to the sample and

subjected to boiling for few minutes. If carbohydrates present in the sample it forms red precipitate of copper oxide.

d) Fehling's solution test: A small amount of sample was heated with dilute hydrochloric acid to hydrolyse polysaccharides. The reaction mixture was neutralized on adding sodium hydroxide solution and then followed by Fehling's solutions 1 and 2 were added. In case of reducing sugars red precipitate of cuprous oxide was formed whereas in case of non reducing sugars on boiling them with acids they will be converted into reducing sugars².

B. Test for alkaloids:

a) Dragendorff 's test: A few mg of plant extract sample was taken and dissolved in 5ml water. Then 2M hydrochloric acid was added until an acid reaction developed. In that mixture, 1ml of Dragendorff 's reagent was added. If alkaloids present in sample extract, it forms orange red precipitate.

b) Wagner's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and acidified with hydrochloric acid (1.5%v/v) a few drops of Wagner 's reagent (iodine potassium iodide solution) was also added to it. If alkaloids present in the sample extract it forms reddish brown precipitate.

c) Mayer's test: A small amount of plant extract sample extract was taken and 2-3 drops of Mayer's reagent (Potassium mercuric iodide solution) in the test tube. If alkaloids present in the sample it forms dull white precipitate.

d) Hagger's test: A few mg of plant extract sample was collected to a test tube and 3ml of Hagger's reagent (saturated aqueous solution of picric acid) was added to it. If alkaloids present in the sample it forms a crystalline precipitates.

C. Test for glycosides:

a) Legal's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and dissolved in pyridine then added sodium nitroprusside solution. Make this solution completely alkaline .If glycosides present in the sample it forms pink red colour.

b)Balijet's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and sodium picrate solution was added. If glycosides present in the sample it forms yellow or orange colour.

c) Borntrager's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and few ml of dilute sulphuric solution was added to it. Then the solution was filtered. Then chloroform and ether was added in to the filtrate and shaken well. To that solution ammonia was added and then the organic layer was separated. If organic layer shows pink, red or violet colour it indicates the presence of glycosides.

D. Test for saponins:

a) 1ml of alcoholic plant sample extract was taken and diluted in 20 ml of distilled water. Then the solution was continuously shaken for 15 min in a graduated cylinder. Then it generates a one centimeter foam layer if saponins are present in the extract.

E. Test for flavonoids:

a) Shinoda test: A small amount plant extract sample was taken and then 5-10 drops of 30 hydrochloric acid was added. Then small pieces of magnesium added to it. If flavonoids present in the sample it forms reddish pink or brown colour.

b) Alkaline reagent test: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and mixed with 2ml of 2% NaOH solution then it produces yellow colour. Again to that solution 2 drops of diluted acid was added in it . If flavonoids present in the extract, yellow colour changes to colourless.

c) Take a filter paper and dip it in a alcoholic solution of the plant sample extract and then add some amount of ammonia solution. If the colour changes from white to orange it indicates the presence of flavonoids.

F. Test for tannins:

a) A small amount of plant extract sample was taken, then few drops of ferric chloride solution was added. If the solution colour changes to dark blue or greenish black colour it indicates the presence of tannins.

b) A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and then potassium cyanide was added to it . If the solution colour changes to deep red colour, it indicates the presence of tannins.

c) A small amount of plant extract sample was taken to a test tube and then few mg of potassium dichromate was added. If the yellow colour precipitate was formed then it indicates the presence of tannins.

d) Catechin test (match stick test): A matchstick is dipped in plant extract sample, then dried near the burner and moistened with concentrated hydrochloric acid. On warming near a flame the matchstick wood turns pink or red due to formation of phloroglucinol.

G. Test for protein and amino acid:

a) Biuret's test: Take 2-3 ml of plant extract sample in a test tube and then add 1ml of sodium hydroxide solution (40%) and 2 drops of copper sulphate solution (1%) and mixed properly. If the solution shows pinkish -violet and purple-violet colour then it indicates the presence of proteins.

b) Ninhydrin's test: A small amount of plant extract sample was mixed with a freshly prepared 2 drops of 0.2% ninhydrin solution and then heated to boiling for 1-2 min and allowed to cooling. If the solution shows

blue colour then it indicates the presence of amino acids, proteins, peptides.

c)Xanthoprotein test: The plant extract sample was taken in a test tube and few drops of concentrated nitric acid was added to it. Then a white precipitate was obtained, upon heating the solution turns to yellow colour and carefully the solution is cooled down. Then 20% of sodium hydroxide solution was added in excess, if the solution produces orange colour then it indicates the presence of amino acids. The orange colour is due to nitration of aromatic ring present in phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan.

d)Millon's reaction: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken in a test tube and few drops of Millon's reagent (mercuric nitrate in nitric acid containing a trace of nitrous acid). If the solution turns red on heating it indicates the presence of amino acids.

H. Test for fats or fixed oils:

a) Using sodium hydroxide: A small amount of plant extract sample was mixed in one ml 1% of copper sulphate solution then 10% sodium hydroxide solution was added. If the solution turns blue colour then it indicates the presence of glycerine.

b) Saponification: A small amount of plant extract sample was taken and mixed with 2% sodium carbonate solution and shaken vigorously and boiled. A clean soapy solution was formed cooled and few drops of concentrated HCL was added and observed that fatty separate out and float up.

c) Filter paper test: Take few drops of plant extract sample in a petri dish and take a filter paper and dip it

in the sample solution. If the filter paper get stained permanently then it indicates the presence of oils¹⁵⁻¹⁹.

Estimation of total flavonoids content (TFC): Estimation of total flavonoids component was based on aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) method. Taken 2.5mg of quercetin component and dissolved in 2.5ml ethanol. Then different aliquots of 5-25µg/ml were prepared in ethanol²⁰. Quercetin was used as standard, 1gm of the dried extract were dissolved with 10ml of ethanol and filter. Three ml of this extract was used for the estimation of flavonoids. Take 3ml of extract or standard and added 1ml of 2% AlCl₃ ethanolic solution, then allowed this mixture to stand at room temperature for 60 min. Then absorbance was measured at 420nm by spectrophotometer²¹.

Antioxidant Activity by Hydrogen peroxide scavenging method:

A solution of hydrogen peroxide(40mM) was prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) Different concentrations (1,2,3,4,5µg/ml) of synthesized compounds (Quercetin) were added to hydrogen peroxide solution (0.6 ml,40mM). Absorbance of hydrogen peroxide at 230nm was determined after 10 minutes against a blank solution containing phosphate buffer without hydrogen peroxide. 20 The simplest way for estimation of IC₅₀ value was then calculated by using equation²¹⁻²⁵.

$$IC_{50}=(0.5-b)/a$$

where, IC₅₀=Half -maximal inhibitory concentration
a=assay value
b=blank value

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Yield of extracts:

According the results of percentage yield it is clear that ethanol was a good solvent for extraction of *T. cordifolia*. The yield of *Tinospora cordifolia* using ethanol and methanol solvents was higher than chloroform solvent .*T. cordifolia* exhibited higher yield in ethanol followed by ethanol extracts.

Table 1: Result of percentage yield of different extracts.

S.no	Solvents	% Yield
1	Chloroform	0.7
2	Methanol	1.8
3	Ethanol	2.5

Results of Phytochemical screening:

Phytochemical analysis of leaf extract of *T. cordifolia* revealed that various phytochemicals such as flavonoids, diterpenes, proteins, saponins ,amino acids and sugars present in different solvent extracts(Table 2).Three different solvents (Ethanol ,methanol and chloroform) were used to obtain leaf extracts used for qualitative phytochemicals screening of plants using

standard phytochemical tests. Phytochemicals analysis is a very useful step in the medicinal plant and subsequently ,it may be used for drug discovery and development. Earlier studied revealed that successfully extractions of phytochemical components depend on the solvent types used in extraction process. In this study, different solvents were used. This study concluded that solvent variation affected the

phytochemical compounds present on the extracts. 21,22,23 Most of the phytochemical components present on ethanol solvent extracts. It has more solubility for bioactive component of *T. cordifolia* than the other solvent extracts. Earlier study revealed that phytochemical analysis of *T. cordifolia* showed that leaf extracts of plant has flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, tannins, steroids and terpenoids. This plant is potential medicinal plant due to variation and availability of phytochemicals. In this study,

qualitative analysis of *T. cordifolia* showed that ethanolic leaves extracts has more phytochemical component such as flavonoids, phenols, amino acids, diterpenes, saponins and proteins. Flavonoids and diterpenes present in all three solvent extracts. Therefore, these different solvent extracts could be seen as a better source of rich phytochemical compounds. Thus, there is no necessary to use these solvents for qualitative analysis of plants.

Table 2 :

S. No	Constituents	Maceration Extract		Soxhlation Extract	
		Result	Colour	Result	Colour
1	Carbohydrates				
	A) Molisch's test	Fail	Yellow	Fail	Yellow
	B) Benedict's test	Fail	Dark blue	Fail	Dark blue
	C) Barfoed's test	Fail	Blue	Fail	Blue
2	Alkaloids				
	A) Dragendorff test	Fail	Brown	Fail	Brown
	B) Wagner's test	Fail	Light brown	Fail	Light brown
	C) Mayers test	Fail	Light yellow	Fail	Light Yellow
3	Glycosides				
	A) Legal test	Fail	Black	Fail	Black
	B) Balijet's test	Fail	Brown	Fail	Brown
	C) Bortrager's test	Fail	Yellow	Fail	Yellow
4	saponins	Fail	Foam layer not formed	Fail	Foam layer not formed
5	Flavonoids				
	Shinoda test	Fail	Light yellow /Brownish colour	Fail	Red
	B) Alkaline Reagent test	Pass	Yellow	pass	Colour less solution
	C) Filter Paper test	Pass	Orange stain	pass	Orange stain
6	Tannins				
	A) Ferric Chloride test	Fail	Greenish black	Fail	Greenish black
	B) Test with potassium dichromate	Fail	Yellow	Fail	Yellow
7	C) Catechin test	Fail	Pink colour	Fail	Colour
	Proteins and Amino acids				
	A) Biuret's test	Fail	Blue	Fail	Blue
	B) Ninhydrin's test	Fail	Black	Fail	Black

	C)Xanthoprotein test	Fail	Light orange	Fail	Orange
	D)Millon s Test	Pass	Red	Pass	Red
8	Fats And Fixed Oils				
	A) Sodium Hydroxide Test	Pass	Blue	Pass	Blue
	B) Saponification test	Pass	Soapy solution	Pass	Soapy solution
	C)Filter Paper test	Pass	Stains appeared	Pass	Stains appeared

Results of total flavonoids content:

Total flavonoids content was determined by the presentation of Quercetin calibration curve. Quercetin was taken as standard in different concentration measured the absorbance of quercetin at 420nm. According to this calibration curve, flavonoids content was determined.

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance At (230nm)
1	5	0.007
2	10	0.053
3	15	0.065
4	20	0.074
5	25	0.105

Result of Antioxidant Activity:

According to present study, T.cordifolia is highly antioxidant plant because the presence of flavonoid component. Thus, antioxidant rich leaf extracts of T.cordifolia serve as a source of nutraceuticals that alleviate the oxidative stress and helps in prevention and reduction of the degenerative disease with consequent health benefits.

Table 3:

S.no	% Inhibition by radical scavenging method concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (mean) λ Max=420 nm	IC 50
1	1	0.032	15.12
2	2	0.020	24.4

3	3	0.041	11.90
4	4	0.023	21.21
5	5	0.016	30.5

CONCLUSION:

India has a large flora which require in traditional treatments of medical system.

After completion of qualitative and quantitative estimation of these plants could be based on their concentration present in given dilutions like 5grms in 250ml and 10 grams in 150 ml of suitable solvents etc. The appearance of flavonoids, diterpenes, saponins, amino acids and proteins which are responsible for these activities and their therapeutic and antioxidant effect of different phytochemicals can be estimate These results revealed that flavonoid component were present in all solvents extracts of *T.cordifolia*.

REFERENCES:

1. Patwardhan B, Gautam M. Botanical immune drugs: scope and opportunities, *Drug Discovery Today*. 2005; 10(7):495– 502.
2. Sharma R, Amin H, Galib R, Prajapati PK. Therapeutic vistas of Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers): a medico historical memoir, *Journal of Research and Education in Indian Medicine*, 2014; XX(2):121-135

3. Sharma R, Amin H, Galib R, Prajapati PK. Antidiabetic appraisal of Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers): insightful exposition of ayurvedic claims, *Rasamruta*, 2014; 6(16):1-14
4. Anonymous. Wealth of India. A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products. 1st ed. Vol. 10. New Delhi: CSIR; 2003, p. 251-252.
5. Khosa RL, Prasad S. Pharmacognostical studies on Guduchi *Tinospora cordifolia* (Miers.), *Journal of Research and Education in Indian Medicine*, 1971; 6:261.
6. Joseph JA, Shukitt-Hale B, Denisova NA, Bielinski D, Martin A, McEwen JJ et al. Reversals of age-related declines in neuronal signal transduction, cognitive, and motor behavioral deficits with blueberry, spinach, or strawberry dietary supplementation, *Journal of Neuroscience*, 1999; 19:8114-21.
7. Hammer KA, Carson CF, Riley TV. Antimicrobial activity of essential oils and other plant extracts, *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 1999; 86(6):985
8. Mukherjee PK. Quality control of herbal drugs. 2nd Ed. Business Horizons; 2007.

- 9.Khandelwal KR. Practical pharmacognosy technique and experiments. 23nd Ed. Nirah Prakashan; 2005.
- 10.Kokate CK. Practical pharmacognosy, 4th Ed. Vallabh Prakashan; 2011.
- 11.Practical pharmacognosy khandelwal k.r.2005.
- 12.https://pharmagrowww.com/soxhletextraction/#Lab_oy_Glass_Soxhlet_Extraction_Apparatus_Set_5550_with_soxhlet_Extraction_Tube_Allihn_Condenser_Extraction_Thimble_Apparatus_Set_Essential_Oil_Extractor_Organic_Chemistry_Lab_Glasswar.
- 13.Sushma Rudraswamy, Brinda Suhas Godhi, Detailed Understanding of Different Extraction Methods For the Research on Medicinal Plants, Indian Journal of Oral Health and Research,2021, XX:XX.
- 14.Mohammed Ali, Pharmacognosy and phytochemistry volume-1
- 15.Aiyelaagbe OO, Osamudiamen PM. Phytochemical screening of active compounds in *Mangifera indica* Leaves from Ibadan, Oyo State Plant Science Research, 2009; 2(1):11- 13.
- 16.Yadav RNS, Agarwala M. Phytochemical analysis of some medicinal plants, Journal of Phytological Research, 2011; 3:10-14.
- 17.Dasgupta S, Parmar A, Patel H. Preliminary phytochemical studies of *Kalanchoe gasteronis-bonnieri*, International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences, 2013; 4:550-7.
- 18.Jakopic J, Veberic R, Stampar F. Extraction of phenolic compounds from green walnuts fruits in different solvents, Acta Agriculturae Slovenica, 2009; 93(1):11-15.
- 19.Koffi E, Sea T, Dodehe Y, Soro S. Effect of solvent type on extraction of polyphenols from twenty three Ivorian plants, Journal of Animal Plant Sciences, 2010; 5 (3):550- 558.
- 20.Flavonoids ck kokate vallabh prakashan 2014. 45 Bapatla college of pharmacy Dept. of Pharmaceutical Chemistry
- 21.Olajuyigbe OO, Afolayan AJ. Flavonoid content and antioxidant property of the bark extract of *Ziziphus mucronata* Willd. Subsp. *Mucronata* Willd, BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine, 2011; 11:130.
- 22.Madhusweta Das, Sneha Schwag, Antioxidant Activity: An Overview, Journal of Science & Technology,2013;2278-2249.
- 23.Kitts DD, Wijewickreme AN, Hu C. Antioxidant properties of a North American ginseng extract, Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry, 2000; 203(1-2):1-10.
- 24.Jang HD, Chang KS, Huang YS, Hsu CL, Lee SH, Su MS. Principal phenolic phytochemicals and antioxidant activities of three Chinese medicinal plants, Food Chemistry, 2007; 103:749-756.
- 25.Premanath R, Lakshmidheri N. Studies on antioxidant activity of *Tinospora cordifolia* (Miers) leaves using invitro models, Journal of American Science, 2010; 6(10):736 743